

DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16740461>

Protective effects of jamun (*Syzygium cumini*) seed and orange (*Citrus sinensis*) peel extracts against lead-induced nephrotoxicity in rats

Akansha Srivastava ^{1,*}, Sunil K. Srivastav ¹, Nobuo Suzuki ², Ajai K. Srivastav ¹¹ Department of Zoology, DDU Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur 273009, India² Noto Marine Laboratory, Institute of Nature and Environmental Technology, Kanazawa University, 927-0553 Ishikawa, Japan Ishikawa, Japan

* Corresponding author e-mail: akanshasri1994@gmail.com

Received: 03 February 2025; Revised submission: 12 May 2025; Accepted: 17 June 2025

<https://jbrodka.com/index.php/ejbr>Copyright: © The Author(s) 2025. Licensee Joanna Bródka, Poland. This article is an open-access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

ABSTRACT: The present study investigated histological changes in the kidney of lead treated rats and also evaluated role of jamun (*Syzygium cumini*) seed and orange (*Citrus sinensis*) peel extracts in protecting the kidney from lead toxicity. Male Wistar rats were divided into six groups, Group A: Control; Group B: Lead (Pb); Group C: Lead and jamun seed extract (Pb+JSE); Group D: Lead + orange peel extract (Pb+OPE); Group E: Orange peel extract (OPE); Group F: Jamun seed extract (JSE). The lead dose was 50 mg/kg body weight (b wt) whereas orange peel and jamun seed extract dose was 200 mg/kg b wt/day. Kidneys were fixed on 15 and 30 day following the treatment. 15 day Pb (Group B) treated rats exhibited shrunken glomeruli while 30 day Pb treated rats revealed tubular degeneration, and glomerular hypertrophy. In Pb+ JSE (Group C) and Pb+OPE (Group D) treated rats for 15 day and 30 day, the kidney exhibits changes similar to those as noticed in Pb exposed rats but to a lesser extent. Kidney of rats treated for 15 and 30 day with Group E (OPE) and Group F (JSE) have not shown any remarkable histological change. The present study clearly indicates that histological structure of kidney can be altered adversely by lead. Also, the present study revealed that lead toxicity to kidney can be protected by supplementation with extracts of jamun seed and orange peel.

Keywords: Lead; *Syzygium cumini*; *Citrus sinensis*; Antioxidant.

1. INTRODUCTION

Heavy metals are referred to as essential elements because they are needed for a number of physiological and biochemical processes that are vital to life. However, at high concentrations, they have the potential to be toxic. Heavy metals bioaccumulate in our systems when they are ingested or breathed in. They are therefore categorized as dangerous. Physiological and metabolic problems are brought on by this bioaccumulation. They have been accumulated in the environment, including our atmosphere, rivers and soils as a result of their extensive usage in agriculture, industry, medicine and other fields [1, 2].

Heavy metals interact with nuclear proteins and DNA to produce damage that is specific to certain sites. There are two possible kinds of damages: "direct" and "indirect". The metal causes conformational changes in the biomolecules during the "direct" damage. However, the generation of reactive oxygen and

nitrogen species results in "indirect" damage caused by the heavy metal. It has been observed that signaling pathways are activated by heavy metals [3].

Metals cannot be broken down since they are non-biodegradable and hence, exist in the environment for a very long time. Until they are eluted to other compartments, heavy metals that are present in soil and sediments stay there for a long time. They may also generate or deteriorate into more hazardous forms in response to reactions with other components of the soil or sediment. In contaminated areas like abandoned mine sites or areas where metal-containing insect repellents were previously used, anthropogenic activity has left an extremely high concentration of metals. Lead (Pb) is a hazardous heavy metal that can cause poisoning and various adverse effects on humans and other animals [4]. It is released as mixed industrial effluents from mechanical units, contaminating marine biological systems and killing organisms. Lead is a naturally occurring pollutant that is extremely dangerous to human health and causes a substantial renal toxicity [5]. Lead has a tendency to accumulate in biological systems. Lead is frequently added to urban water storage and is typical of water bodies [6].

According to Segal *et al.* [7] the bulk of heavy metals found in marine ecosystems are the result of both natural and man-made processes, and they may be dangerous to living beings. Industrial workers also constantly consume lead and are subject to acute poisoning. They are exposed to lead at work when they work in battery recycling factories or smelters. The greatest public health risk connected with lead is currently exposure of young children to decomposing fragments of leaded paint. Lead exposure in children may now occur from contaminated drinking water due to outdated infrastructure. Consuming heavy metals poses a major risk to human health, especially when lead contaminated food is involved. As a result, it is essential to use methods that lessen lead toxicity [8].

Aerobic organisms have developed an extensive array of antioxidative and repair systems for the prevention of oxidative stress chemicals that break down ROS, like catalase (CAT), superoxide dismutase (SOD), glutathione peroxidase (GPx), and glutathione reductase (GR) give the primary antioxidant defense. In contrast, ROS-induced damage repair systems eliminate damaged cells through autophagy and apoptosis processes [9]. The potential to protect human organs from oxidative damage by enhancing antioxidant defenses in the body and increasing total antioxidant capacity is demonstrated through use of nutritional antioxidants as complementary substances that delay or prevent oxidation of cellular components [10].

In India, the deep purple colored, oblong edible fruit with a large centrally located seed is commonly known as Jamun (*Syzygium cumini*). Jamun's fruits pulp and seed extract has been used medicinally for many years. Antigenotoxic effects of the medicinal seed extract are obtained from *Syzygium cumini*, Skeels (Synonym: *Eugenia jambolana*; Family Myrtaceae) [11]. Jamun has anti-ulcer, anti-free radical scavenging, anti-diabetic, anti-malarial, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antipyretic, anti-allergic, anti-bacterial, gastro-protective and radio-protective properties [12].

It is also possible to use orange peel extracts in a one step, easy, economical and green strategy for sustainability of dyeing and acquiring wool using high antioxidant activity polyamides or fabrics with multifilament cellulose acetate which has an antioxidant and antibacterial activity [13]. Hesperidin, a component of *Citrus sinensis* that is found in orange peels, has antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer, and antilipidemic properties. Orange peels contain naringin and naringenin, which have antibacterial, antidiabetic, and antitoxic properties [14-16].

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Male Wistar rats (40-60 g) were purchased from Asia Scientific Emporium, Varanasi, India. Prior to treatment, rats were acclimatized for at least two weeks in polypropylene cages. Rats were given standard diet and water *ad libitum* throughout the acclimatization and treatment. Rats were randomly divided into 6 groups- A, B, C, D, E and F and each group contained 10 animals. Following treatments were given orally to each group daily at 8:00 AM throughout the experiment:

- Group A: Control
- Group B: (Lead (Pb) - treated): Rats were given daily with lead (50 mg/kg body weight (b wt)).
- Group C: (Lead + jamun seed extract): These rats were given daily lead (50 mg/ kg body wt) and jamun seed extract (200 mg/kg b wt) simultaneously.
- Group D: (Lead + orange peel extract): These rats were given daily lead (50 mg/kg b wt) and orange peel extract (200 mg/kg b wt) simultaneously.
- Group E: (Orange peel extract): Rats received daily orange peel extract (200 mg/kg body wt).
- Group F: (Jamun seed extract): Rats received daily jamun seed extract (200 mg/kg body wt).

On the 15th and 30th day after initiation of the experiment, rats (5 from each group at each interval) after overnight fasting, were lightly anesthetized after 24 hours of the last dose.

Seeds of jamun (*Syzygium cumini*) were bought from commercial supplier (M/S SVM Naturals, Tamil Nadu, India). Purchasing of oranges (*Citrus sinensis*) were done locally and separation of peels were done. The jamun seeds and orange peels were washed with tap water and dried at room temperature. They were grinded in powdered form. These powdered forms were mixed with 90% ethanol in 1:20 ratio (w/v) and kept on orbital shaker for 48 h and then filtered with the Whatman No. 1 filter paper and kept in rotatory evaporator at 40 °C. The dried materials were kept at -20 °C for future experiment. Soxhlet apparatus was not used in this process because of heat labile compound present in leaves may be denatured. During the treatment, rats received dose of dried residues mixed with ethanol.

Fixed tissues of kidney were dehydrated in a gradient series of ethanol, cleared with xylene and embedded in paraffin. Sections were cut at 6 µm and placed on slides. The sections were cleared in xylene and rehydrated with graded series of alcohol and stained with hematoxylin and eosin (HE) solution for light microscopic analysis. Photomicrographs of stained slides were taken with the help of Olympus H-20i microscope and Olympus E 420 camera.

Experimental design was approved by the Research Degree Committee, D.D.U. Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur, India. The study was conducted in accordance with “Guide for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals”.

3. RESULTS

Kidney of control rats is composed of nephrons. Each nephron consists of a dilated portion, the proximal tubule, distal tubule, loop of Henley and the renal corpuscles. Renal corpuscles consists of tufts of capillaries. Glomerulus is surrounded by the Bowman’s capsule. Urinary space is present between the glomerulus and Bowman’s capsule (Figure 1).

Shrunken glomeruli were observed at certain places with kidney following 15 day lead treatment (Group B), forming a gap between the glomerulus and Bowman's capsule (Figure 2). In rats from Group C and Group D changes were similar to Group B but to a lesser extent.

After 30 days of lead treatment, swollen glomeruli were observed at certain places, resulting in no space between Bowman's capsule and glomerulus (Figure 3). In addition, there was degeneration of the proximal and distal tubules (Figure 4). In the lumen of proximal and distal tubules, eosin positive deposits have also been observed at certain sites. Few glomeruli appeared to be degenerated (Figure 5). Similar changes were observed except degeneration in proximal and distal tubules of Group C and Group D rats. The renal morphological structure is almost the same as that of control in Group E and Group F rats.

Figure 1. Kidney of control rat. Hematoxylin-eosin X 500.

Figure 2. Kidney of 15 day lead exposed rat showing shrunken glomeruli (arrows). Hematoxylin-eosin X 100.

Figure 3. Kidney of 30-day lead exposed rat showing glomerular hypertrophy (arrows). Hematoxylin-eosin X 500.

Figure 4. Kidney of 30 day lead exposed rat showing tubular degeneration (arrows). Hematoxylin-eosin X 500.

Figure 5. Kidney of 30 day lead exposed rat showing glomerular degeneration (arrows). Hematoxylin-eosin X 500.

4. DISCUSSION

The shrinkage of glomeruli observed in rats exposed to lead treatment is in conformity with the findings of few workers who have also observed glomerular shrinkage in rats after exposure to toxicants/chemicals- paraquat [17], lithium [18], aluminium chloride [19], chlorpyrifos [20], cadmium [21, 22], 2,3,7,8-tetrachlorodibenzo-p-dioxin [23], endosulfan [24], silver [25], malathion [26], mercuric chloride [27], 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D) [28], MCLR [29], cypermethrin [12] and bisphenol-A [30].

Glomeruli in rats treated with lead showed degeneration after 30 days of treatment. In past few researchers have observed similar results following toxicant exposure in fish after treatment with chlorpyrifos [31], deltamethrin [32], cadmium [33], microcystin [34] and cypermethrin [35]; in chick- after treatment with cypermethrin [36] and in rat- after treatment with paraquat [37], chlorpyrifos [20] and cadmium [22,23], lead [38], MCLR [29] and cypermethrin [12]. Additionally, Barrouillet *et al.* [39] observed a decrease in GFR following lead exposure and proposed that glomerular degeneration is the cause of decrease in GFR.

In rats tubular degeneration following lead treatment after 30 days were noticed. Similar findings were reported by other researchers in vertebrates after exposure to chemicals or toxicants to fish: chlorpyrifos [31], cadmium [33], microcystin [34], cypermethrin [40]; to chick: cypermethrin [36]; to quail: lead [41]; to wood mouse and white-toothed shrew (landfill leachates containing toxic metals [42]; to mice: chlorpyrifos [43], microcystin [44]; to rabbit: fluoride [45]; to rat: chlorpyrifos [20, 46], microcystin [29,47], metal mixture [48], paraquat [17,37], cypermethrin [12,49], fenthion [50], cigarette smoke [51], cadmium [21,22], lead [38],

gentamicin [52], 2,4-D [53], zinc [54], streptozotocin [55], monosodium glutamate [56], endosulfan [24], lead acetate [57]. However, when fish are exposed to bifenthrin, kidney morphology does not change [59].

After 30 day of treatment with lead rats exhibited glomerular hypertrophy which is in conformity with the reports of other investigators who have also noticed similar changes after exposure to different toxicants in rats: cadmium [21,22], gentamicin [52], 2,4-D [53], chlorpyrifos [20], *Acacia nilotica* pod extract [55], heterogenous chemical mixture [60], fenitrothion [61], malathion [62]. In rabbits fluoride exposure resulted in glomerular hypertrophy [45].

The hydrolytic alterations that kidney tubules may experience following toxicant exposure could be the plausible cause of the tubular vacuolization and degeneration observed in rats treated with lead. Similar suggestion has also been proposed [11, 29] for the alteration noticed in toxicant exposed rats.

Author Contributions: AS conducted the data collection and primary investigation for the study, and writing manuscript; SKS and AKS supervised the research, provided guidance throughout the study; SKS, AKS and NS assisted in manuscript writing, formatting and reviewed the final draft. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Ethical Approval: Experimental design was approved (RC/ F.Sc./Zoo/2019-20/13/22) by the Research Degree Committee, D.D.U. Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur, India. The study was conducted in accordance with “Guide for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals”.

Conflict of Interest: The authors of this work declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

Source of Funding: The research work has not been funded by any funding agency.

Acknowledgements: Authors are thankful to Prof. Ravi Kant Upadhyay, Head of Department of Zoology, DDU Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur, India, for providing laboratory facilities.

REFERENCES

1. LennTech. (2017) Heavy Metals. <https://www.lenntech.com/processes/heavy/heavy-metals/heavy-metals.htm>
2. Briffa J, Sinagra E, Blundell R. Heavy metal pollution in the environment and their toxicological effects on humans. *Heliyon*. 2020; 6(9): e04691.
3. Valko M, Morris H, Cronin M. Metals, toxicity and oxidative stress. *Curr Med Chem*. 2005; 12: 1161-1208.
4. Li B, Jin D, Yu S, Etareri Evivie S, Muhammad Z, Huo G, Liu F. In Vitro and In Vivo Evaluation of *Lactobacillus delbrueckii* subsp. *bulgaricus* KLDS1.0207 for the Alleviative Effect on Lead Toxicity. *Nutrients*. 2017; 9(8): 845.
5. Gluhcheva Y, Pashkunova-Martic I, Schaier M, Vladov I, Stoykova S, Petrova E, Pavlova E, Dorkov P, Helbich TH, Keppler B, Ivanova J. Comparative Effects of Deferiprone and Salinomycin on Lead-Induced Disturbance in the Homeostasis of Intrarenal Essential Elements in Mice. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2022; 23(8): 4368.
6. Levin R, Zilli Vieira CL, Rosenbaum MH, Bischoff K, Mordarski DC, Brown MJ. The urban lead (Pb) burden in humans, animals and the natural environment. *Environ Res*. 2021; 193: 110377.
7. Nogueira LS, Bianchini A, Smith S, Jorge MB, Diamond RL, Wood CM. Physiological effects of five different marine natural organic matters (NOMs) and three different metals (Cu, Pb, Zn) on early life stages of the blue mussel (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*). *PeerJ*. 2017; 5: e3141.
8. Srivastav A, Srivastav SK, Upadhyay RK. Physiological and behavioral effects of lead poisoning in aquatic and marine animals: a review. *World J Pharma Pharmaceut Sci*. 2024; 13: 171-185.
9. Zhao X, Zhang Q, Zheng R. The interplay between oxidative stress and autophagy in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Front Physiol*. 2022; 13: 1004275.
10. Macvanin MT, Gluvic Z, Zafirovic S, Gao X, Essack M, Isenovic ER. The protective role of nutritional antioxidants

- against oxidative stress in thyroid disorders. *Front Endocrinol.* 2023; 13: 1092837.
11. Arun R, Prakash MV, Abraham SK, Premkumar K. Role of *Syzygium cumini* seed extract in the chemoprevention of in vivo genomic damage and oxidative stress. *J Ethnopharmacol.* 2011; 134(2): 329-333.
 12. Srivastava BD, Srivastav M, Srivastav SK, Urata M, Suzuki N, Srivastav AK. Protective effects of jamun (*Syzygium cumini*) seed and orange (*Citrus sinensis*) peel extracts against cypermethrin induced nephrotoxicity in rats. *Egypt J Basic Clin Pharmacol.* 2021; 11: 101492.
 13. Prakash C, Prasad MR, Kumar A, Mishra D, Chaudhary A, Srivastav SK. Protective effect of ZnCl₂ on toxicity produced by Microcystin-LR on serum calcium and phosphate levels of freshwater catfish *Heteropneustes fossilis*. *Int J Pure App BioSci.* 2016; 4: 111-117.
 14. Srivastava BD, Srivastav AK. Hepatoprotective effects of extracts of *Syzygium cumini* seeds and *Citrus sinensis* peels against microcystin LR-induced toxicity in rat. *Int J Zool Invest.* 2017; 3: 95-105.
 15. Srivastava BD, Srivastava M, Srivastav SK, Suzuki N, Srivastav AK. Cypermethrin-induced liver histopathology in rat: Protective role of jamun seed and orange peel extracts. *Iran J Toxicol.* 2018; 12(4): 25-30.
 16. Chagas VT, Coelho RMRS, Gaspar RS, da Silva SA, Mastrogiovanni M, Mendonça CJ, et al. Protective effects of a polyphenol-rich extract from *Syzygium cumini* (L.) skeels leaf on oxidative stress-induced diabetic rats. *Oxid Med Cell Longev.* 2018; 2018: 5386079.
 17. Abdel-Mageid SA. Structural changes in the kidney of albino rat in response to the administration of paraquat herbicide. *J Egypt Germ Soc Zool.* 1994; 15: 153-175.
 18. Sharma SD, Iqbal M. Lithium induced toxicity in rats: a hematological, biochemical and histopathological study. *Biol Pharma Bull.* 2005; 28(5): 834-837.
 19. Okail HA, Ibrahim A S, Badr AH. The protective effect of propolis against aluminum chloride-induced hepatorenal toxicity in albino rats. *J Basic Appl Zool.* 2020; 81: 1-11.
 20. Tripathi S, Srivastav AK. Nephrotoxicity induced by long-term oral administration of different doses of chlorpyrifos. *Toxicol Indust Health.* 2010; 26: 439-447.
 21. Tripathi S, Srivastav AK. Cytoarchitectural alterations in kidney of Wistar rat after oral exposure to cadmium chloride. *Tissue Cell.* 2011; 43:131-136.
 22. Srivastava A, Upadhyay RK, Srivastav SK, Suzuki N, Srivastav AK. Protective effects of jamun (*Syzygium cumini*) seed and orange (*Citrus sinensis*) peel extracts against cadmium induced nephrotoxicity in rats. *Int J Zool Invest.* 2024; 10(2): 1149-1158.
 23. Ciftci O, Ozdemir I, Vardi N, Beytur A and Oguz F. Ameliorating effects of quercetin and chrysin on 2,3,7,8-tetrachlorodibenzo-p-dioxin-induced nephrotoxicity in rats. *Toxicol Indust Health.* 2012; 28(10): 947-954.
 24. Khan S. Study of histopathological changes induced by endosulfan in kidney of albino rats. *J Drug Deliv Ther.* 2014; 4(3): 125-128.
 25. Roda E, Barni S, Milzani A, Dalle-Donne I, Colombo G and Coccini T. Single silver nanoparticle instillation induced early and persisting moderate cortical damage in rat kidneys. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2017; 18(10): 2115.
 26. Mamun MAA, Rahman A, Belal SH, Islam MA, Sarker MEH, Arman MSI, Hoque KMF. Histological study of the effect of malathion on liver and kidney tissues of mice model. *Int J Pharm Sci Res.* 2015; 6(3): 1043.
 27. Langeswaran K, Selvaraj J, Ponnulakshmi R, Mathaiyan M, Vijayaprakash S. Protective effect of Kaempferol on biochemical and histopathological changes in mercuric chloride induced nephrotoxicity in experimental rats. *J Biol Active Prod Nat.* 2018; 8(2): 125-136.
 28. Upadhyaya AM, Rao MV, Jhala DD. Ameliorative effects of melatonin against 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid toxicity in kidney of mice-A histological study. *Asian J Pharm Clin Res.* 2018; 11(1): 78-82.

29. Srivastava BD, Srivastava M, Urata M, Suzuki N, Srivastav AK. Efficacy of jamun *Syzygium cumini* seed and orange *Citrus sinensis* peel extracts against microcystin LR induced histological damage in the kidney of rat. *Braz J Biol Sci.* 2020; 7(17): 247-259.
30. Ishtiaq A, Ijaz MU, Ehsan N, Imran M, Naz H, Alvi K, Zhu GP. Therapeutic effect of oroxylin a against bisphenol A induced kidney damage in rats: a histological and biochemical study. *Pak Vet J.* 2022; 42(2): 511-516.
31. Srivastava SK, Tiwari PR, Srivastav AK. Effects of chlorpyrifos on the kidney of freshwater catfish, *Heteropneustes fossilis*. *Bull Environ Contam Toxicol.* 1990; 45: 748-751.
32. Cengiz EI. Gill and kidney histopathology in the freshwater fish *Cyprinus carpio* after acute exposure to deltamethrin. *Environ Toxicol Pharmacol.* 2006; 22: 200-204.
33. Wangsongsak A, Utarnpongsa S, Kruatrachue M, Ponglikitmongkol M, Pokethitiyook P, Sumranwanich T. Alterations of organ histopathology and metallothionein mRNA expression in liver barb, *Puntius gonionotus* during subchronic cadmium exposure. *J Environ Sci.* 2007; 19: 1341-1348.
34. Atencio L, Moreno I, Prieto A, Moyano R, Molina AM, Camean AM. Acute effects of microcystin MCLR and MCRR on acid and alkaline phosphatase activities and pathological changes in intraperitoneally exposed tilapia fish (*Oreochromis sp.*). *Toxicol Pathol.* 2008; 36: 449-458.
35. Korkmaz N, Cengiz EI, Unlu E, Uysal E, Yanar M. Cypermethrin-induced histopathological and biochemical changes in Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*), and the protective and recuperative effect of ascorbic acid. *Environ Toxicol Pharmacol.* 2009; 28:198-205.
36. Aslam F, Khan A, Khan MZ, Sharaf S, Gul ST, Saleemi MK. Toxicopathological changes induced by cypermethrin in broiler chicks: Their attenuation with vitamin E and selenium. *Exp Toxicol Pathol.* 2009; 62: 451-450.
37. Lamfon HA, Al-Rawi MM. Effect of antox and paraquat-induced histological and biochemical changes in kidney of albino rats. *J Appl Sci Res.* 2007; 3: 988-993.
38. El-Newesy MS, El-Sayed YS. Influence of vitamin C supplementation on lead-induced histopathological alterations in male rats. *Exp Toxicol Pathol.* 2011; 63(3): 221-227.
39. Barrouillet MP, Potier M, Cambar J. Cadmium nephrotoxicity assessed in isolated rat glomeruli and cultured mesangial cells: Evidence for contraction of glomerular cells. *Exp Nephrol.* 1999; 7: 251-258.
40. Ayoola SO, Ajani EK. Histopathological effects of cypermethrin on juvenile African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*). *World J Biol Res.* 2008; 1: 1-14.
41. Almansour MI, Al-Otaibi NM, Alarifi SA, Ibrahim SA, Jarra BM. Histological and histochemical alterations induced by lead in the kidney of the quail *Coturnix coturnix*. *Saudi J Biol Sci.* 2008; 15: 307-313.
42. Sanchez-Chardi A, Penarroja-Matutano C, Borrás M, Nadal J. Bioaccumulation of metals and effects of a landfill in small mammals Part III: Structural alterations. *Environ Res.* 2009; 109: 960-967.
43. Thijssen S, Maringwa J, Faes C, Lambricht I, Van Kerkhove E. Chronic exposure of mice to environmentally relevant, low doses of cadmium leads to early renal damage, not protected by blood or urine cadmium levels. *Toxicol.* 2007; 229: 145-156.
44. Al-Majeed MIA, Al-Sultan EYA, Abbas AAK. Toxic effects of low concentration of cyanotoxin (Microcystin-LR) on mice and study of protective efficacy of the antioxidants vitamins (C&E) and *Capparis spinosa* L. root extract. *J Nat Sci Res.* 2016; 6: 34-42.
45. Shashi A, Singh JP, Thapar SP. Toxic effects of fluoride on rabbit kidney. *Fluoride.* 2002; 35: 38-50.
46. Tanvir EM, Afroz R, Chowdhury MAZ, Gan SH, Karim N, Islam MN, Khalil MI. A model of chlorpyrifos distribution and its biochemical effects on the liver and kidneys of rats. *Human Exp Toxicol.* 2016; 35(9): 991-1004.
47. Hooser SB, Beasley VR, Lovell RA, Carmichael WW, Haschek WM. Toxicity of microcystin-LR, a cyclic heptapeptide hepatotoxin from *Microcystis aeruginosa* to rats and mice. *Vet Pathol.* 1989; 26: 246-252.

48. Jadhav SH, Sarkar SN, Patil RD, Tripathi HC. Effects of subchronic exposure via drinking water to a mixture of eight water-contaminating metals: a biochemical and histopathological study in male rats. *Arch Environ Contam Toxicol*. 2007; 53: 667-677.
49. Muthuviveganandavel V, Muthuraman P, Muthu S, Srikumar K. A study on low dose cypermethrin induced histopathology, lipid peroxidation and marker enzyme changes in male rat. *Pest Biochem Physiol*. 2008; 91: 12-16.
50. Kerem M, Bedirli N, Gurbuz N, Ekinci O, Akkaya T, Sakrak O, Pasaoglu H. Effects of acute fenthion toxicity on liver and kidney function and histology in rats. *Turk J Med Sci*. 2007; 37: 281-288.
51. Kuru M, Ugras M, Esrefoglu M. Effect of resveratrol on tubular damage and interstitial fibrosis in kidneys of rats exposed to cigarette smoke. *Toxicol Indust Health* 2009; 25: 539-544.
52. Abdel-Raheem IT, Abdel-Ghany AA and Mohamed GA. Protective effect of quercetin against gentamicin-induced nephrotoxicity in rats. *Biol Pharma Bull*. 2009; 32(1): 61-67.
53. Tayeb W, Nakbi A, Trabelsi M, Miled A, Hammami M. Biochemical and histological evaluation of kidney damage after sub-acute exposure to 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic herbicide in rats: involvement of oxidative stress. *Toxicol Mech Methods*. 2012; 22(9): 696-704.
54. Faddah LM, Baky NAA, Al-Rasheed NM, Al-Rasheed NM, Fatani AJ, Atteya M. Role of quercetin and arginine in ameliorating nano zinc oxide-induced nephrotoxicity in rats. *BMC Compl Altern Med*. 2012; 12(1): 1-14.
55. Omara EA, Nada SA, Farrag ARH, Sharaf WM, El-Toumy SA. Therapeutic effect of *Acacia nilotica* pods extract on streptozotocin induced diabetic nephropathy in rat. *Phytomedicine*. 2012; 19(12): 1059-1067.
56. Dixit SG, Rani P, Anand A, Khatri K, Chauhan R, Bharihoke V. To study the effect of monosodium glutamate on histomorphometry of cortex of kidney in adult albino rats. *Renal Failure*. 2014; 36(2): 266-270.
57. Aksu DS, Saglam YS, Yildirim S, Aksu T. Effect of pomegranate (*Punica granatum L.*) juice on kidney, liver, heart and testis histopathological changes, and the tissues lipid peroxidation and antioxidant status in lead acetate-treated rats. *Cell Mol Biol*. 2017; 63(10): 33-42.
58. Ahmed MS, Massoud AH, Derbalah AS, Al-Brakati A, Al-Abdawani MA, Eltahir HA, Elmahallawy EK. Biochemical and histopathological alterations in different tissues of rats due to repeated oral dose toxicity of cymoxanil. *Animals* 2020; 10(12): 2205.
59. Velisek J, Svobodova Z, Piackova V. Effects of acute exposure to bifenthrin on some haematological, biochemical and histopathological parameters of rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*). *Vet Med*. 2009; 54: 131-137.
60. Morya K, Vachhrajani KD. Impairment of renal structure and function following heterogeneous chemical mixture exposure in rats. *Indian J Exp Biol*. 2014; 52: 332-343.
61. Afshar S, Farshid AA, Heidari R, Llkhanipour M. Histopathological changes in the liver and kidney tissues of Wistar albino rat exposed to fenitrothion. *Toxicol Indust Health*. 2008; 24: 581-586.
62. Hafez EHH, El Atrash AM, Massoud AAN, Attia MFAAA. The impact of the organophosphate insecticide Malathion on rat and the possible ameliorating role of Thymoquinone. *Egypt J Exp Biol (Zool)*. 2017; 13(2): 309-318.